

SOCIAL SITUATION IN ADOLESCENCE

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Abstract: This article discusses the socialization of a teenager, how the social situation is transformed in consciousness into completely new value orientations, the teenager begins to intensively reflect himself, on others, on society. He places accents: family, school, peers acquire new meanings and meanings. For a teenager, there are shifts in the scale of values. Everything is illuminated by the projection of reflection, especially the closest ones: home, family.

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In every family, the child receives the first basics of communication, the very first communication takes place in the womb, the child feels the emotional state of the mother, she begins to talk to him. After birth, the child gets the opportunity to communicate with other family members. This is a stream of speech turns, emotions, feelings. The family gives a great potential for the development of the child's speech. It is constantly necessary to communicate with the child, while correctly pronouncing each letter, word. In the initial stage of the child's development, parents can control the vocabulary. Further, the child's social circle expands, and vocabulary replenishment does not depend on the parents. Puberty occurs in adolescence, which affects consciousness and thinking. The teenager begins to analyze what he has read, heard, and draw conclusions. The family prepares the child for socialization, that is, behavior in society.

The social situation in adolescence as a condition of development and being in adolescence is fundamentally different from the social situation in childhood not so much for external circumstances as for internal reasons. A teenager continues to live in a family (or in a boarding school), study at school (or college), he is surrounded for the most part by the same peers. However, the social situation itself is transformed in his mind into completely new value orientations - the teenager begins to reflect intensely on himself, on others, on society. Now the accents are placed differently: family, school, peers acquire new meanings and meanings. For a teenager, there are shifts in the scale of values. Everything is illuminated by the projection of reflection, first of all the closest ones: home, family.

In a family setting. A teenager, as a rule, lives with his family. He entered the family through his birth, got used to his loved ones the way they get used to them in childhood. Now it's time to evaluate loved ones.

As a child, the child was immersed in the field of seed identification. The family "We" is the first group that is taken for granted in childhood. Parents themselves, relatives, the world of things belonging to them, family traditions, the style of relationships in childhood are perceived as the unchanging essence of being. However, gaining experience of life, a teenager discovers diverse family relationships that differ from the parent family. At the same time, he begins to feel the need to part with the family identity, dissolving him in the bosom of the family. He feels the need for a more universal, broader identity and at the same time in strengthening his own sense of personality, in separating his "I" from the family "We". Therefore, the teenager turns his critical eye to family traditions, values and fetishes.

The family itself takes the same positions in relation to the teenager.

Usually, a family treats a teenager in accordance with established family (and ancestral) traditions. Here we will find a continuation of the same parenting styles that were aimed at the child in childhood.

A family with high reflection and responsibility understands that the child is growing up and that this must be taken into account by changing the style of relationships. A teenager begins to be treated taking into account the sense of adulthood that has appeared in him. Without imposing their attention, parents express their willingness to discuss his problems. "How are you doing, Peter?", "I'm ready to listen to you, Peter", "I can help you with this, Peter". In this way, adults from well-reflecting families express their willingness to cooperate with the teenager. The main thing in such a family is to preserve the sense of self-respect so desired for adolescence.

The character of a teenager from a family with high reflexivity and responsibility develops quite well (unless, of course, there are no prerequisites depressing this development). He builds his relationships with others (adults and peers) mainly according to an adequately loyal type. The value orientations of a teenager in such a family are aimed at penetrating into the values of the entire diversity of reality: the objective world, figurative-sign systems, nature, the very social space of direct human relations. High reflection of the environment creates favorable conditions for the spiritual development of a teenager.

The family is alienated. In this family, a teenager is treated the same as in childhood - they are not interested in him, avoid communicating with him and keep a distance from him. Alienated parents have already made their contribution to the development of their child's character: he either also became the bearer of

alienated forms of behavior and the owner of an alienated soul, or he developed a bitter inferiority complex. Tendencies in the development of his character as a way of interacting with other people are already clearly manifested: nihilistic reactions prevail, exaggerated aggression or inadequate loyalty, passive style of behavior.

A teenager in such a family feels superfluous. For the most part, he rushes to the street to his peers, where he seeks satisfaction in communication. The style of communication with peers duplicates, as a rule, the ways of his interaction in the family. An estranged family may limit the child's development opportunities.

The authoritarian family, according to established stereotypes, continues to impose the same strict requirements on the teenager as in childhood. Usually, if it was accepted earlier, physical punishments continue to be used here (in childhood, they were spanked, now they can "punch"). In an authoritarian family, a teenager is just as lonely, unhappy and insecure as in childhood. However, the tendencies of his character development are already clearly emerging: he becomes the bearer of an authoritarian way of interacting with people or, on the contrary, demonstrates humiliated inadequate loyalty, passivity, behind which there is a high neuroticism of an insecure teenager. An authoritarian family can also limit a teenager's development opportunities.

A family with a conniving attitude. In such a family, the principle of permissiveness continues to prevail: the teenager has long been "sitting on the head" of his parents and has mastered the ways of manipulating them well. Selfishness and the conflict that accompanies it are the main characteristics of the character of teenagers from such families. Here the teenager is doubly unhappy: age itself is already a crisis of personal development, plus more shortcomings formed in his personal position by permissiveness relationships, which real life will never offer him.

A teenager from a family with a permissive style of attitude towards him usually does not assimilate positive forms of communication: adequate loyalty is not known to him. He relies on those ways of influencing others that have successfully fed his egoism all the years of his life in the family, aggression (which is expressed in unreasonable intolerant demands - "I want it so!", "I said it!") and nihilism. A conniving family deprives a teenager of the opportunity to realize the laws of social relations and makes him untenable in real relationships with others.

The family is overprotective. A teenager in such a family grew up under the close attention and care of parents who have a lot of their own internal problems, arising mostly on the basis of personal tragedies and complexes. Parents still do not part with the teenager, they take care of him not only from the outside, but also seek to take possession of his emotional experiences. Here, the teenager, as in childhood, is unsure of himself. If necessary, he can't fight back, but he can't build a

positive relationship himself. He is passive, compulsively loyal. He is infantile in his social reactions and his peers are already reacting to this feature, giving him childish nicknames like "Baby", "Mama's Son", "Kindergarten", etc.

The described styles of relationships to a teenager demonstrate only trends in the conditions of personality development in adolescence. Real life can be softer, more prosperous, but also tougher, more terrible, incomprehensible. A family can have many different communication styles at the same time, due to the heterogeneity of the cultural levels of its members (grandparents, parents, other relatives). A teenager may seek to identify with his parents, but may also take an alienated position.

The probability of living in ideal family conditions for a teenager is also very difficult because he now begins to produce his own ways of communication, learned in the family, which often alarms and amazes parents: "How dare you talk to me like that!", "The milk on his lips is not dry, but he is there too!" and etc. Having got used to the complete dependence of their child in childhood, parents at first do not agree to release their boy from the place reserved for him. However, normal, mentally healthy, loving parents still strive to solve emerging problems with their grown-up children. They do their best to provide the teenager with a sense of security, to create conditions for normal existence and development.

At the same time, the boy, in search of his "I", alienating himself from his parents and at the same time loving them as before, learns to take into account very different plans of human feelings and actions. He learns anew - now at the level of age-related alienation - to build new relationships with his family - with those who raised and cared for him - according to his own understanding. Through life collisions in the family, a teenager discovers that the world is not divided into "white" and "black", that it is impossible to calculate relationships purely arithmetically. Of course, a teenager does not suddenly approach these simple discoveries. But he begins to accumulate experience and learn understanding and compromises.

Teenagers living in degraded families, where parents fight, take alcohol, drugs, and debauchery, usually become infected with these ailments in childhood. A teenager can be classified as an alcoholizing or narcotic group if such offenses are repeated often enough (1-2 times a month). But even if he only tasted a forbidden potion from the hands of parents who had lost control, he thereby violated normative social prohibitions. For a teenager who has not yet tasted the forbidden potion, the motivational readiness to use alcohol or drugs is also extremely high. In some happy cases, a teenager from an alcoholizing, drugging or dissolute family begins to resist degradation so actively that he has enough spiritual strength to escape from the conditions of existence offered by life and go his own way.

In a single-parent family (there is often no father here), a teenager begins to feel especially uncomfortable. After all, it is during this period that there is an acute sense of need for a father, because sexual identification in adolescents is carried out in relation to parents of both sexes. In addition, for a teenager, his general social situation is very significant, which is formed, among other things, by the composition of the family. The presence of both parents positively represents a teenager among peers. The absence of a father weakens his social position.

A teenager in foster care is a difficult problem in adolescence, especially if he knows that his father and mother are not biological parents. If he is lucky and he has found a good family, he still constantly experiences internal tension and uncertainty about how his adoptive parents treat him. At the same time, he is also concerned about how his peers personally evaluate him due to the fact that he does not have a blood family.

A special problem in the modern Russian family is the relationship about the material and financial dependence of a teenager. Until recently (until 1991), teenagers in the vast majority of cases were completely dependent on the financial situation of the family and on the pedagogical views of parents regarding the pocket money of the grown-up child. Adults often used this "lever", trying to bring their child to obedience. The teenager often found himself in a dead end: he longed for freedom and could not get rid of such an offensive financial dependence. The consequences of such a situation turned out to be sad: they led to escapes from home, to theft, to group robbery, and sometimes to suicide attempts. Of course, not only financial problems have been and remain a source of confrontation in the family of adults and teenagers.

Today, the economic situation is different; teenagers can earn honestly by selling newspapers, washing cars, working as couriers, etc. However, the opportunity to earn some money on your own can also bring some tension into family relations. Parents who warm up the idea that "we feed and water you, dress and shoe you" risk that one day, feeling "economically independent", a teenager loudly, with a cynical grin, will offer to reimburse expenses or separate and eat and dress themselves separately. In addition, tension in the family can also cause external social problems.

Gaining financial independence in our time is very dangerous for teenagers from a social and psychological point of view. In Russia, there are no traditional ways for them to earn money yet. A teenager can easily become involved in shady financial relationships of adults. Therefore, the problem of "Children and money" is very relevant for every family in which children grow up.

Money, being a sign of well-being, at the same time acts as the equivalent of a thing. A teenager evaluates things belonging to the family as prestigious or as

having no value. A modern teenager can, based on the criteria of the value of things, begin to evaluate his family as "rich" or as "poor". The evaluation of material items belonging to the family or absent from the family can become a criterion for the merits of parents.

Such tendencies are especially acute at historical moments that produce a fracture, upheaval, fracture, transformation and other radical perestroika. So, today in Russia, the assessments that were previously formed in the culture take on different meanings: the attitude to the subject world, to interpersonal relations is being rebuilt. The place of an individual or family among other people is now determined to a greater extent than before, not only by personal qualities, but also by serving things that represent them in social relations (house, apartment, works of art, banknotes, land and other prestigious things at a particular moment in the development of society). Today, society is in a state of marginality, which directly affects adolescents who are sensitive to social phenomena.

Special conditions of life in adolescence - stay in residential institutions. If teenagers are here from the first years (from infancy) and an early age, they adapt to life in such an institution. They feel quite well the specifics of the relationships of the adults serving here, they are guided in their official and unofficial hierarchy and, based on their real behavior, they know their value well. At the same time, a teenager living in a boarding school is quite finely oriented in the hierarchy of interpersonal relationships and intuitively strives to find his place in it. As mentioned above, even in childhood, children spontaneously develop orphanage solidarity, expressed in the position of "We". This psychological education, although it arises in childhood, but it is really formed in adolescence. "Their own" enjoy protection outside the home in front of those from the family - these are "strangers". There is a special normativity here: someone else can be held (and this will be the subject of special boasting). At the same time, the orphanage teenager is fully aware of the possible consequences.

Teenagers deprived of parental care have a lot of problems that are unknown to their peers from a normal family. These teenagers are psychologically alienated from people ("They"), and this gives them freedom to commit offenses. Crowding in all rooms leads to the need to constantly contact others, which creates emotional tension, anxiety and at the same time increases aggression. In the conditions of boarding school, adolescents develop an aggressive, ignoring or passive type of behavior and emotional response. An adequate loyal type of behavior is formed extremely rarely if a teenager has inner strength and his value orientations direct him to identify with an ideal or with a real person, happily met by him.

A teenager who got into a boarding school from a good family as a result of tragic circumstances (the unexpected death of both parents, for example) turns out

to be doubly unhappy: on the one hand, he suffers because of such tragic orphanhood - unexpected deprivation of parents, on the other - because of new, unknown conditions of existence for him. In a residential institution, the style of relationships between both adults and children terrifies him. A teenager, due to his small life experience, his lack of formation as a person, feels his stay in a boarding school as the collapse of his whole life.

Feeling the fundamental difference of a newcomer who arrived from a prosperous family, the boarding school teenagers themselves can begin to oppress him, taking revenge on him for his prosperous former life. There are many nuances here - after all, each new entrant brings his own culture, his own special personality from another, also special life, into the communication of peers. However, a strong spiritually, a leader by nature, a newcomer can lead his peers from an orphanage.

No matter how the conditions of life in adolescence develop, the orientation towards family and the need for it during this period of life are extraordinary.

From this we conclude that children in adolescence feel separation very strongly, become more vulnerable, lock themselves in. Aggressive behavior of adolescents can be provoked by aggressive beliefs and attitudes, a high degree of hostility in the environment in which a teenager grows up, impulsivity characteristic of adolescence, an unformed ability to emotional and social self-regulation.

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